

Robotics for Precision Agriculture @DIAG

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Abstract

Flourish¹ is a recent H2020 project, whose aim was to develop a multi-platform robotic solution for precision agriculture, combining a micro UAV and a UGV. The aim of this document is to sketch the contribution of Sapienza Univ. of Rome in the context of the Flourish project, as well as the current follow-up activities in precision agriculture.

1 Introduction

The Flourish project started in 2014 with the aim of showing through a prototype system the potential of autonomous robots to support the practices of Precision Agriculture. Specifically, the project focus was on targeted weed removal, to reduce the use of pesticides and human labor. The prototype system is composed of a micro UAV for aerial surveying of the crop field and a UGV (i.e. Bosch BoniRob) for operation in the field. The overall Flourish concept is shown in Fig. 1. The Flourish consortium was led by ETH Zurich and includes seven partners, among them RoCoCo lab from Sapienza Univ. of Rome. Below we address the scientific contributions developed at Sapienza Univ. of Rome.

2 Research highlights

The main results achieved by our group in Flourish are in the following research areas: (i) Crop/weed classification; (ii) UGV localization and field mapping; (iii) UGV and UAV map realignment.

Flourish *software* and the *Datasets* are available at:

www.dis.uniroma1.it/~labrococo/fsd

2.1 Crop/weed classification

The basic step for limiting weeds is their identification on the field. In particular crop/weed classification aims at spotting cultivated plants and weeds from top views of the field. This problem can be effectively addressed by convolutional neural networks; however, this approach suffers from the effort in input data labeling, that requires a manual pixel-wise annotation. We proposed to use synthetic images generated by a representation of the field built through *Unreal Engine 4* (see

¹<http://flourish-project.eu/>

an example in 2) to support the training of the network. In [Potena *et al.*, 2017b; Di Cicco *et al.*, 2017] we report that the use of the simulated images, whose annotation comes directly from the simulation environment) can substantially reduce the amount of labelled real images, while keeping the same classification accuracy ($\sim 91\%$).

Figure 1: Flourish concept: UAV and UGV collaboratively map and act upon the weeds.

Figure 2: Synthetic image of a sugar beet field annotated.

2.2 UGV localization and field mapping

The goal of this research was to solve the Simultaneous Localization and mapping problem for the UGV. In fact, GPS alone is not fully satisfactory, because it is not always sufficiently accurate, even in the most advanced technologies on the market, considering the navigation requirements for the UGV moving in between narrow crop rows. Moreover, the scene is rather homogeneous and does not provide good enough features for data association. Our work aims at improving the overall system performance by combining a variety of sensors (shown in 3) to leverage their capabilities and

compensate their limitations. In addition, we exploit some contextual features, such as local planarity and row structure to obtain the required accuracy (mean error of ~ 7 cm).

Figure 3: Bosch Bonirob: the UGV used in Flourish.

2.3 UGV and UAV map realignment

In order for Flourish heterogeneous robots to exchange information a shared representation of the field is required. In addition to the mentioned difficulties of scene analysis in the agricultural scenario, the UAV and UGV acquire images of the field from radically different perspective, and the maps that are produced are affected by scale errors and missing parts (see Fig. 4). Hence, the state-of-the-art 3D registration approaches are failure prone. Our approach [Potena *et al.*, 2019] is based on the idea to turn the 3D matching problem into a 2D realignment. To this end, the maps produced by the UGV and the UAV are first aligned, based on GPS and IMU data; subsequently they are projected into 2D models and, finally they are aligned using an algorithm for *Large Displacement Optical Flow*, suitably adapted to the context at hand. Our experimental results show that the proposed approach can align maps with a scale error up to 30% and initial estimation errors up to 5 meters.

Figure 4: Overview of the map alignment developed in Flourish

3 Follow-up

In the last year after the project ended, we have further developed our research in two main directions: (i) the solution of specific challenges for the agricultural domain, exploiting

tools and know-how acquired in Flourish; (ii) the development of a comprehensive simulation environment for the agricultural domain. In the first respect, we have developed an approach for mapping the sunflower plants in the field that are affected by *Peronospora* [Rodríguez-Gómez *et al.*, 2019]. The mapping of the infected plants can be used to identify the areas where they should be removed from the field. Another recent contribution, is focused on the improvement of the approach for crop/weed classification [Fawakherji *et al.*, 2019]. Finally, we have addressed target-based navigation on the UAV to allow for accurate inspection of plants from the UAV [Potena *et al.*, 2017a].

In the second line of research, we have merged all the developments based on simulation to create a general simulation environment that can serve the development of robotic solutions both in improving the perception tasks, and for testing to complex UAV missions. The potential advantages offered by a dedicated simulation environment are manifold and investigated in other domains, such as autonomous cars. We are currently looking at simulating plants at different growth stages, fields in different lighting conditions and models of additional sensors used in agriculture (e.g. infrared).

References

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